

Spectrophotometric Determination of Zirconium with Thorin and *N*-Hydroxy-*N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine

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Many spectrophotometric methods for the determination of trace amount of zirconium in complex materials have been reported, using various organic dyes and reagents¹. These methods are tedious, need rigid control of pH, temperature and reagents, and are not selective as most of the common ions and anions associated with zirconium interfere. The classical thorin method also suffers from interference of other elements which give coloured complex with thorin².

In the present investigation, Zr^{IV} has been selectively extracted with HDPBA in presence of thorin as an ion-associated floated complex in benzene-ethanol (3 : 7) mixture at pH 2.2. Most of the common ions associated with zirconium do not interfere in the present method. Moreover, this method increases the sensitivity over 6-folds as compared to the classical thorin method.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectrum of Zr^{IV}-thorin-HDPBA complex formed in benzene-ethanol mixture shows λ_{\max} around 495 nm. Complete extraction of the complex in presence of thorin is achieved with 2.78×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ to 3.4×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ HDPBA at an optimum pH range of 1.0–3.5. At least 8.5×10^{-5} to 2.5×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ thorin is required for maximum colour development. Of the various solvents used, benzene was chosen due to its superiority. And ethanol as diluent was found to give maximum and constant colour intensity of the complex. A shaking time of 2 min is sufficient for complete extraction of the complex which is stable up to 4 h at room temperature (25°).

The Zr^{IV}-thorin-HDPBA complex obey Beer's law up to $4.0 \mu\text{g cm}^{-3}$ of Zr^{IV}. The molar absorptivity of the complex calculated in terms of Zr^{IV} is $1.82 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ at λ_{\max} 495 nm. The Sandell's sensitivity of the method is $0.005 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$. The relative standard deviation of the method was found to be $\pm 1.4\%$. The detection limit of Zr^{IV} is $0.05 \mu\text{g cm}^{-3}$.

A large number of ions do not interfere in the present method. However, Th^{IV}, Fe^{III} and U^{IV} interfere. The interference of Th^{IV} and Fe^{III} is eliminated by masking with 1 cm³ of 5% EDTA and that of U^{IV} by oxidation of U^{IV} to U^{VI} with 0.1 cm³ concentrated perchloric acid treatment. The following diverse ions (amount in mg given in pa-

renthesis) do not interfere in the determination of $4.0 \mu\text{g cm}^{-3}$ of Zr^{IV}: U^{IV} (0.5); Th^{IV} (0.75); fluoride, Fe^{III} (0.8); Pb^{II}, Cu^{II} (1.0); Ni^{II}, Cd^{II}, Zn^{II}, Sn^{II} (1.2); Nb^V, Mo^{VI} (3.5); W^{VI}, Re^{VII} (5.0); Pd^{II}, Ga^{III} (6.0); Al^{III}, Sb^{III}, Co^{II} (6.5); Cr^{III}, Hg^{II}, Mn^{II} (7.0); Mg^{II} (8.0); acetate, tartarate (15.0); thiourea (16.0); EDTA (18.0); perchlorate (20.0).

Application : The present method was applied for the recovery of zirconium from standard samples and synthetic mixtures. The standard samples were prepared as according to the literature³. The recovery of Zr^{IV} from synthetic mixtures prepared similarly to enriched standard samples, was examined and was found to be satisfactory. Aliquots of this solution was taken for analysis of Zr^{IV} as in the recommended procedure. The metal content of the samples were compared with AAS. The results obtained are summarised in Tables 1 and 2.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF Zr^{IV} IN STANDARD SAMPLES

Standard samples	Zr Content (ppm)		RSD of present method* $\pm\%$
	Certified value	Present method	
USGS**			
BHVO-I	145.0	145.2	1.7
BIR-I	18.4	18.2	1.5
MAG-I	128.0	128.9	1.5

*n = 5. **United States Geological Survey Standards, Arlington VA, U.S.A

TABLE 2—RECOVERY OF Zr^{IV} IN SYNTHETIC MIXTURES

Sl. no.	Ion (Amount, μg)	Zr found μg	RSD of present method ($\pm\%$)*
1.	Zr ^{IV} (15) + U ^{IV} (60) + Cr ^{III} (300) + Al ^{III} (1000) + Mo ^{VI} (2000) + Co ^{II} (700)	14.8	1.6
2.	Zr ^{IV} (20) + U ^{IV} (90) + Cr ^{III} (400) + Al ^{III} (1200) + Mo ^{VI} (2500) + Co ^{II} (900)	19.6	1.5

*n = 3.

Experimental

A Carl-Zeiss Jena 'Spekol' spectrophotometer and a Systronics 335 pH meter were used. All chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade (B.D.H. and E. Merck).

A stock solution of Zr^{IV} was prepared by dissolving zirconyl oxychloride (0.8834 g) in 4 mol dm⁻³ HCl. The working standard solution was prepared by appropriate dilution. A 0.0017 mol dm⁻³ thorin was prepared in glass-

distilled water. A $0.0035 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ solution of *N*-hydroxy-*N,N'*-diphenylbenzamidine⁴ (HDPBA) in benzene was employed. HCl-KCl buffer solution⁵ (pH 2.2) was used.

Procedure : To an aliquot of the solution containing up to $40 \mu\text{g Zr}^{\text{IV}}$ was added thorin solution (1 cm^3) and its pH was adjusted to 2.2 by adding HCl-KCl buffer solution in a total volume of 10 cm^3 aqueous phase. Then 0.1% HDPBA solution (3 cm^3) in benzene was added to it and the mixture was shaken vigorously for 2 min. The aqueous phase was discarded and the red-orange coloured complex formed at the interface was washed with buffer solution ($2 \times 2 \text{ cm}^3$). The absorbance of the floated complex was measured after dissolution in ethanol to a total of 10 cm^3 at $\lambda_{\text{max}} 495 \text{ nm}$ against the reagent blank.

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